

Prevalence of Disabled People in India

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ABSTRACT

During the students life, learning is the main thing. But in students learning process, disability condition can cause barriers in education. Disability can have direct impact on students learning. Nature of the disability can display the learning capacity of students. There are many kind of disabilities like physical disabilities, visual impairment, hearing impairment, speech & language disorders, intellectual disabilities including learning disabilities & autism spectrum disorder. According to Census 2011, in India, out of 121 Cr population, about 2.68 Cr persons are disabled that means 2.21% of the total population. A large number of disabled individuals comprised both children and young adults in South 24-Parganas district of West Bengal. 14.71% were diagnosed as significant hearing impairments in the Medinipur Sadar Subdivision, Paschim Medinipur district, West Bengal. Finding displayed that majority of respondents was men than women. The disability rates was 1635 per 100000 population in Tamil Nadu according to 2011 Census. It was observed that the prevalence rate of students with learning disability varies from 10.76% to 13.41% with mean percentage of 12.31 in two districts of Haryana. Besides that, Prevalence of disability/100000 population by types, residence and sex in India, 2011 and the total number of individuals associated with disability in West Bengal Disability Census, 2011 is also written. To prevent disability, good nutrition is needed when the child is in womb. Care is also needed and it is necessary to hear the disabled persons voice or any kind of signals that he/she delivers.

Keywords: Disability, Disabled Persons, Census, West Bengal, India

INTRODUCTION

During the students life, learning is the main thing. But in students learning process, disability condition can cause barriers in education. Disability can have direct impact on students learning. Nature of the disability can display the learning capacity of students (Rehabilitation Council of India, 2016). According to Census 2011, in India, out of 121 Cr population, about 2.68 Cr persons are disabled that means 2.21% of the total population (Social Statistics Division, Government of India, 2016). 56% are males and 44% are females among the disabled population. Disability has of many types like physical disabilities, visual impairment, hearing impairment, speech & language disorders, intellectual disabilities including learning disabilities & autism spectrum disorder (Social Statistics Division, Government of India, 2016).

Burden of disability in India

Disability itself is a huge term that covering multidimensional impairments, limitation of activity and restrictions of participations. In body structure and function, impairment is a problem; activity limitation means limitation of activity due to disability; participation restriction means individuals cannot participate properly in any event in our society due to disability. Disability is not a simple characteristic (complex). Disabled peoples has a many kind of communication problem with our society. They are also the most neglected individuals in human society. 400 millions of peoples with disabilities were found in Asia alone. In 2011, prevalence of disability/100000 population by types, residence and sex in India was 1983. In world population, 650 million peoples (10%) live with disability while India has 2.68 Cr (Census 2011) peoples live with disability. The percentage of disabled persons in India are 2.21 (Paul and Saha, 2015).

Table 1: Disability percentage of rural and urban area and in social group in India (Saikia et. al. 2016)

Country	Male	Female
India	2.60	2.16
Type of residence		
Rural	2.66	2.20
Urban	2.46	2.07
Social group		
Scheduled Caste (SC)	2.98	2.44
Scheduled Tribe (ST)	2.58	2.27
All others	1.92	1.59

Table 2: Age-standardized disability prevalence for Indian sub-populations and states (in %) (Saikia et. al. 2016)

States	Male	Female
Andhra Pradesh	3.04	2.56
Assam	1.88	1.77
Bihar	2.72	2.15
Chhattisgarh	3.07	2.67
Delhi	1.76	1.45
Gujarat	2.10	1.75
Haryana	2.58	2.11
Himachal Pradesh	2.60	2.08
Jammu & Kashmir	3.54	3.08
Jharkhand	2.89	2.46
Karnataka	2.42	2.02
Kerala	2.44	1.99
Madhya Pradesh	2.56	2.10
Maharashtra	3.02	2.38
Odisha	3.40	2.96
Punjab	2.66	2.11
Rajasthan	3.00	2.67
Tamil Nadu	1.83	1.45
Uttar Pradesh	2.46	2.03
West Bengal	2.53	2.12
Uttarakhand	2.20	1.81
Goa	2.39	2.20
Arunachal Pradesh	2.56	2.54
Manipur	2.20	1.94
Meghalaya	1.85	1.71
Mizoram	1.75	1.55
Nagaland	2.07	1.97

Table 2: Age-standardized disability prevalence for Indian sub-populations and states (in %) (Saikia et. Al)

States	Male	Female
Sikkim	3.61	3.68
Tripura	2.05	1.75
Andaman & Nicobar islands	2.20	1.85
Lakshadweep	2.72	2.66
Chandigarh	1.67	1.42
Puducherry	2.79	2.21
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	1.28	1.16
Daman & Diu	1.21	1.16

Extension of Table 2

Table 3: Prevalence of disability/100000 population by types, residence and sex in India, 2011

Disability	No. of individuals
In seeing	392
In hearing	432
In speech	169
In movement	294
Mental disability	-
Mental Retardation	111
Mental Illness	52
Any Other	404
Multiple Disability	128
Total	1983

Source: Census of India, 2011

Table 4: West Bengal Disability Census, 2011

Age Group	Total	Male	Female
0-4	82491	43841	38650
5-9	132038	72742	59296
10-19	334013	185773	148240
20-29	319203	181629	137574
30-39	281601	161631	119970
40-49	277116	162907	114209
50-59	222050	129857	92193
60-69	192803	103419	89384
70-79	115677	57575	58102
80-89	43062	20229	22833
90+	14350	5913	8437
Age Not Stated	3002	1665	1337
Total	2017406	1127181	890225

Table 5: West Bengal Disability Census, 2011

Age Group	Seeing	Hearing	Speaking	Movement	Mentally Retarded	Mentally Illness	Others	Multiple Disability
0-4	17639	14260	2359	8029	4087	687	28155	7275
5-9	23245	19725	16087	13426	9022	2627	31479	16427
10-19	59293	49354	34720	42751	30021	10869	68164	38841
20-29	54386	46645	27508	49373	27342	12841	73105	28003
30-39	52910	43810	22376	43803	23455	13668	60913	20666
40-49	60181	43532	19576	43703	19729	12742	55696	18957
50-59	55265	35171	12141	43145	11809	8564	39876	16079
60-69	53553	32001	7613	40665	6854	5544	26820	19753
70-79	32758	20211	3339	23713	2815	2689	12494	17658
80-89	11162	7512	966	8650	832	937	3933	9070
90+	3386	2385	421	2426	343	275	1508	3606
Age Not Stated	695	586	230	261	214	72	778	166
Total	424473	315192	147336	322945	136523	71515	402921	196501

Burden of Disability in South 24-Parganas, West Bengal

A study was done on Evaluation of registered visually disabled individuals in a district of West Bengal, India. 155 (310 eyes) visually disabled individuals were involved in this study from medical records of South 24-Parganas district. 131 (84.52%) individuals had 100% disability. The higher number of disabled individuals were males than in females. 58 (37.42%) disabled individuals were below 21 years of age. A large number of disabled individuals comprised both children and young adults (Ghosh et.al. 2008).

Prevalence of Hearing Impairment in the Paschim Medinipore district, West Bengal, India

A study was occurred on Prevalence of Hearing Impairment in the Medinipur Sadar Subdivision, Paschim Medinipore district, West Bengal, India. 700 individuals were involved in this study. The procedure taken includes interviews, questionnaires, and physical examination and Audiology Division of Midnapore Rehabilitation Centre for Children, Midnapore. Out of 700 individuals, 103 (14.71%) were diagnosed as significant hearing impairments. Finding displayed that majority of respondents was men than women (Chatterjee and Bhuniya, 2012).

Burden of Disability in Tamil Nadu, India

A study was occurred on Prevalence of hearing impairment in school children (aged 8-14 years) in the villages of Vadamavanthal, Tamil Nadu, India. Using pre-tested questionnaire, the school students were interviewed and aural examination was completed by a qualified otolaryngologist. Among 700 school children between the age of 8-14 years, this study was conducted. Among 700 school children 216 (30.9%) were suffering from hearing impairment. In the age group of 8 years, it was more prevalent followed the age group of 14 years. Hearing impairments can leads to poor academic achievement and can affect the child's vocational choices in future (Norman et. al. 2016).

Another study was found on Prevalence of disability in Tamil Nadu, India. Here is the analysis of disability rates per 100000 population based on the 2011 Census cross-sectional survey data of Tamil Nadu. 1179963 disabled individuals were found in Tamil Nadu according to 2011 Census. The disability rates was 1635 per 100000 population. Movement disability, hearing disability and sight disability accounted for 24%, 19% and 11% of total respectively. Physical and mental disability were found in 1.6% of the population of Tamil Nadu (Velayutham et. al. 2017).

Table 6: Age-standardized disability rates per 100000 individuals according to the type of disability in districts of Tamil Nadu, 2011

District	Disability rates per 100000 individuals			
	Seeing	Hearing	Speech	Movement
Thiruvallur	204	499	97	358
Chennai	226	501	86	298
Kancheepuram	186	341	93	382
Vellore	167	261	116	407
Tiruvanmalai	186	249	137	403
Viluppuram	190	312	121	480
Selam	137	180	96	390
Namakkal	174	253	101	447
Erode	161	246	111	408
Nilgiris	152	208	85	343
Dindigul	139	327	133	335
Karur	143	170	113	408
Tiruchirappalli	162	196	109	407
Perambalur	190	368	198	393
Ariyalur	231	357	192	496
Cuddalore	220	372	101	362
Nagapattinam	200	258	114	471
Thiruvarur	238	446	149	486
Thanjavur	148	225	107	414
Pudukkottai	164	217	124	386
Sivaganga	177	342	120	447
Madurai	181	275	100	380
Theni	148	317	155	411
Virudhunagar	148	223	118	428
Ramanathapuram	186	349	124	390
Thoothukkudi	212	303	115	512
Tirunelveli	169	272	109	477
Kanniyakumari	145	295	106	454
Dharmapuri	203	269	136	507
Krishnagiri	172	270	126	416
Coimbatore	168	352	92	288
Tiruppur	123	245	94	310
Average	176.56	296.81	118.06	409.18

Extension of Table 6

Table 7: Age-standardized disability rates per 100000 individuals according to the type of disability in districts of Tamil Nadu, 2011

District	Disability rates per 100000 individuals			
	Mental retardation	Mental illness	Multiple	Any other
Thiruvallur	132	36	135	566
Chennai	119	57	103	539
Kancheepuram	140	44	119	442
Vellore	138	42	136	309
Tiruvanamalai	136	36	134	278
Viluppuram	120	36	131	337
Selam	115	33	107	189
Namakkal	131	34	114	228
Erode	133	49	139	261
Nilgiris	139	42	117	268
Dindigul	129	38	115	304
Karur	130	43	129	157
Tiruchirappalli	162	47	128	263
Perambalur	146	37	136	371
Ariyalur	148	43	171	354
Cuddalore	137	32	119	310
Nagapattinam	183	69	167	283
Thiruvarur	162	61	160	369
Thanjavur	166	58	139	248
Pudukkottai	150	53	156	277
Sivaganga	168	52	163	327
Madurai	144	42	108	316
Theni	145	40	129	333
Virudhunagar	150	43	141	235
Ramanathapuram	160	49	134	342
Thoothukkudi	172	76	141	262
Tirunelveli	170	60	135	280
Kanniyakumari	178	86	153	447
Dharmapuri	127	38	156	279
Krishnagiri	115	30	116	313
Coimbatore	124	38	102	324
Tiruppur	108	39	119	300
Average	143.03	46.34	132.87	315.96

Extension of Table 7

Table 8: Average disability (seeing, hearing, speech, movement, mental retardation, mental illness, multiple, any other) rates per 100000 individuals in Tamil Nadu state.

District	Disability rates per 100000 individuals							
	Seeing	Hearing	Speech	Movement	Mental retardation	Mental illness	Multiple	Any other
Average	176.56	296.81	118.06	409.18	143.03	46.34	132.87	315.96

Prevalence of learning disabled students in two districts of Haryana

A study was occurred on Identification and prevalence of learning disabled students in Haryana. This study objective was to identify and know the prevalence of learning disability among class fifth children. The sample consisted of all the students studying in class fifth of five schools in Kurusshetra and Jind districts of Haryana. The tools used were both informal and formal academic result of previous class (English and mathematics), Checklist for identifying learning disabled students by teachers/parents, Ravens progressive matrices (intelligence test) and Diagnostic test of learning disability (Swaroop and Mehta 2005). It was observed that the prevalence rate of students with learning disability varies from 10.76% to 13.41% with mean percentage of 12.31 (Kumar and Suman, 2017).

Table 9: Prevalence of students with learning disabilities in five school of Haryana (Velayutham et. al. 2017)

Serial Number	School Name	Number of students	Number of students with learning disability	Percentage of students
1.	School I	82	11	13.41
2.	School II	68	8	11.76
3.	School III	53	6	11.32
4.	School IV	73	10	13.69
5.	School V	65	7	10.76
Total		341	42	12.31

Summary and Conclusion

According to Census 2011, in India, out of 121 Cr population, about 26.8 Cr persons are disabled that means 2.21% of the total population. The percentage of disabled persons in India are 2.21. A large number of disabled individuals comprised both children and young adults in South 24-Parganas district of West Bengal. 14.71% were diagnosed as significant hearing impairments in the Medinipur Sadar Subdivision, Paschim Medinipore district, West Bengal. Finding displayed that majority of respondents was men than women. 1179963 disabled individuals were Census. The disability rates was 1635 per 100000 population. Movement disability, hearing disability and sight disability accounted for 24%, 19% and 11% of total respectively. Physical and mental disability were found in 1.6% of the population of Tamil Nadu. It was observed that the prevalence rate of students with learning disability varies from 10.76% to 13.41% with mean percentage of 12.31 in two districts of Haryana. It is concluded from the present review that prevalence of disabled persons in India. Magnitude of disability is more observed in males than in females.

Future Scope

The present review displays that disability is major public health problems in India, their magnitude (prevalence) is estimated in 2011 Census. Possibly, It is hoped that again will census will happen in 2019. In future, many study can be done with about disabled persons. Following below study may be good about disabled persons in future.

Census is needed again to know the burden of disabled person in India. Small study is also needed to know the percentage of magnitude persons in many places of India. Many types of disability is observed in India, that is why, every types need separately studied. Study may be done on problems of disabled persons. Further research may be conducted on disabled persons by taking variables like attention, interest, intelligence, academic performance and motivation, parents and teachers attitude. A comparison can also be studied between disabled children who study in special school and those who study in other schools with normal children.

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References

- [1] Chatterjee and Bhuniya, (2012), Prevalence of hearing impairment in the Medinipur Sadar Subdivision, Paschim Medinipore district, West Bengal, India, *International Journal of Science and Research*, 3(10): 786-791.
- [2] Ghosh S, Mukhopadhyay S, Sarkar K, Bandyopadhyay M, Maji D, Bhaduri G, (2008), Evaluation of registered visually disabled individuals in a district of West Bengal, India, *Indian Journal of Community Medicine*, 33(3): 168-171.
- [3] Kumar and Suman, (2017), Identification and prevalence of learning disabled students, *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 7(3): 317-319.
- [4] Norman P, Chandran M, Dhandapani T, (2016), Prevalence of hearing impairment in school children (aged 8-14 years) in the villages of Vadamavanthal, Tamil Nadu, India, *International Journal of Community Medicine and public Health*, 3(12): 3369-3373.
- [5] Paul and Saha, (2015), Burden of disability in India, *Journal of Multidisciplinary Research in Healthcare*, 2(1): 31-54.
- [6] Rehabilitation Council of India, (2016), Disability and Implications on Learning, 1-90.
- [7] Saikia N, Bora JK, Jasilionis D, Shkolnikov VM, (2016), Disability Divides in India: Evidence from the 2011 Census, *PLoS ONE*, 11(8)e0159809, doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0159809.
- [8] Social Statistics Division, Government of India, (2016), Disabled Persons in India: A statistical profile 2016, 1-107.
- [9] Velayutham B, Kangusamy B, Mehendale S, (2017), Prevalence of disability in Tamil Nadu, India, *The National Medical Journal of India*, 30(3): 125-130.